

A Model-based Stochastic Augmented Lagrangian method for Online Stochastic Optimization

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Abstract - In this paper, we focus on online stochastic optimization problems in which the random parameters follow time-varying distributions. In each time slot t , a sample is drawn from the current distribution after making the decision. Then the new lost function and the constraint function are updated. Due to the setting of the online problem framework, we use dynamic regret and constraint violation to measure the performance of our algorithm. For solving the online stochastic optimization problem, we propose a model-based stochastic augmented Lagrangian method for online stochastic optimization, which is referred to as MSALM. In each time slot, we construct the model functions for the objective and constraint functions based on their properties, which reduced the computational complexity. The step size is designed in a dynamic form and decreases as t increases to accelerate convergence. Under the assumptions, we prove that the algorithm's regret and violation have a sublinear bound of total number of slots T . We design simulation experiments to verify the efficiency of our online algorithm. Its performance is evaluated on a range of information and system engineering problems, including adaptive filtering, online logistic regression, the time-varying smart grid energy dispatch problem, the online network resource allocation problem, and the path planning problem. In addition, in the context of the path planning problem, we integrate our algorithm with supervised learning to demonstrate its enhanced capabilities. The experimental results validate the performance of our new algorithm in practical applications.

Keywords: online stochastic optimization, time-varying distribution, augmented Lagrangian method, machine learning, network resource allocation.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, stochastic optimization and online convex optimization have garnered widespread attention in various fields, including machine learning, signal processing, and

control. In the field of online convex optimization, the player makes decisions sequentially according to feedback from the environment. The meaning of the online process is clearly defined in several classic review articles[19, 13, 5]. Many algorithms are proposed to solve time-varying constrained online convex optimization like in[4]. However, random factors such as noise and disturbances are present in the environment, so we cannot receive all the information we need accurately. In the real environment, the distribution of random variables is unknown. For example, the joint distribution of input features and labels is unknown for learner in machine learning. Cao et al. [3] proposed an algorithm to solve such problems. But research on this kind of issue is still very limited at present. Thus, we aim to design an algorithm to solve online stochastic optimization with time-varying distribution.

Under the online optimization framework, we reformulate subproblems at all time slots as stochastic optimization tasks. This type of problem has been studied in references such as[15]. We studied stochastic gradient-based algorithms such as [18], which gave us some insights. Since the distributions of stochastic parameters vary over time, we design an online stochastic optimization framework that better reflects real-world conditions. In online stochastic optimization, after deciding on each time slot, we draw new samples from the current distribution, update the loss and constraint functions, and sequentially obtain optimal solutions. Traditional deterministic online optimization algorithms often use the global optimum as a performance measure, as seen in [20, 11, 16, 2]. However, since distributions are time-varying in our setting, traditional performance metrics become inadequate. We therefore adopt dynamic evaluation criteria. In related work, Cao et al. [3] introduced the concept of dynamic optimal point drift to measure the degree of distributional change. Their findings show that the algorithm performs well when the drift is not too large. We continue to use this setting.

For constrained optimization problems, several literature use the Lagrangian method, for example[1, 8, 7, 9, 17]. Especially for online convex optimization, [12] shows that the augmented Lagrange method converges super-linearly asymptotically. This method has good performance for some specific structured questions. Promoting this method, Liu et al.[10] proposed model-based augmented Lagrangian methods and demonstrated that MALM is better than several existing online primal-dual methods based on Lagrangian. Inspired by this idea, we design a model-based stochastic augmented Lagrangian method for online stochastic optimization with time-varying distribution. Recent studies on distributed online optimization with coupled constraints[14] and online composite optimization with time-varying regularizers[6] also provide valuable insights into handling dynamic and structured online optimization problems, further motivating our approach.

The following are the main contributions of our work:

1. We propose a model-based stochastic augmented Lagrangian method for online stochastic optimization. In each time slot, the model functions for the objective and constraint functions are constructed based on their properties, which reduced

the computational complexity. We design the step size in a dynamic form and decreases as t increases to accelerate convergence.

2. We adopt dynamic regret and constraint violation as our performance metrics. These measures are particularly suited for online stochastic optimization under time-varying distributions. Under the assumptions, we prove that the algorithm's regret and violation have a sublinear bound of the total number of slots T .
3. We demonstrate the practical efficacy of our proposed algorithm through a series of simulation experiments. In the contexts of adaptive filtering and online logistic regression, we compare our method with the projected stochastic gradient descent (PSGD) algorithm[3]. The results show that MSALM attains lower regret and constraint violation bounds than PSGD, indicating that its ability to converge more rapidly toward the theoretical optimum while maintaining stricter adherence to constraints. In addition, results from the time-varying smart grid energy dispatch, online network resource allocation, and path planning problems collectively confirm that regret and violation have bounds $O(\sqrt{T})$.

Organizations. In section 2, we introduce a restarting FISTA method and a first-order trust region method, then present the RFISTA-SVRG-TR algorithm. In section 3, we prove the linear convergence analysis of the RFISTA-SVRG-TR algorithm when the objective function is strongly convex. In section 4, we show the performance of our method through numerical experiments. Finally, in section 5, some conclusions are given.

2. MSALM for online stochastic optimization

In this section, we first present the framework of online stochastic optimization problems. Then we provide our algorithm and some details about the update strategies.

2.1 *The online stochastic optimization problem*

The online stochastic optimization problem can be viewed as a multi-round learning process.

In the round (or time slot) t , the player makes a decision $x_t \in X$, where X is a set of admissible actions. After that, the player receives a new loss (objective) function f and constraint function g by determining the random parameter. $f(x, \theta)$ and $g(x, \xi)$ are loss and constraint functions, where $\theta \in \Theta$ is a random parameter (Θ is the set of possible realizations of the random parameter) and $\xi \in \Xi$ (Ξ is the set of possible realizations of the random vector). $g : R^n \times R^l \rightarrow R^m$ represents m constraints. According to these messages, the optimization problem is as follows,

$$\min f_t(x) := E_{\theta \sim P_t}[f(x, \theta)]$$

$$\text{s.t. } g_t(x) := E_{\xi \sim Q_t}[g(x, \xi)] \leq 0, t \in \{1, 2, \dots, T\}$$

where P_t and Q_t are the unknown distributions of the random parameter θ and ξ at time t .

In this paper, $\|\cdot\|$ is determined to be a 2-norm. On this basis, we have some standard assumptions.

Assumption 1. The set X is bounded, i.e., there is a constant $R > 0$ such that $\|x - y\| \leq R$ for any $x, y \in X$.

Assumption 2. $f(x, \theta)$ and $g(x, \xi)$ is convex and differentiable for any $\theta \in \Theta$ and $\xi \in \Xi$.

Assumption 3. The Slater's condition holds, i.e., there are a constant $\varepsilon_0 > 0$ and a decision $x_t \in X$ at the time t such that $g_t^{(i)}(x_t) \leq -\varepsilon_0, i = 1, 2, \dots, m$.

2.2 MSALM algorithm

For solving the problem in the above framework, we design an algorithm based on model-based augmented Lagrangian methods. Model-based means that we conservatively approximate the loss function and constraint function based on the properties of functions. We let $\hat{f}_t(x)$ and $\hat{g}_t(x)$ be the approximations to $f_t(x)$ and $g_t(x)$ at the point x_t . The approximations we made satisfy the following conditions,

Assumption 4. The approximate functions should be convex and satisfy the following conditions,

1. For any $x \in X$ except the point x_t , $\hat{f}_t(x) \leq f_t(x)$ and $\hat{g}_t(x) \leq g_t(x)$.
2. At the point x_t , $\hat{f}_t(x_t) = f_t(x_t)$ and $\hat{g}_t(x_t) = g_t(x_t)$.
3. $\hat{g}_t(\cdot) = [\hat{g}_t^{(1)}(\cdot), \hat{g}_t^{(2)}(\cdot), \dots, \hat{g}_t^{(m)}(\cdot)]$ is bounded on X , i.e. there is a constant $D > 0$ such that $\|\hat{g}_t(x)\| \leq D$ for any $x \in X$.

Therefore, the approximate optimization problem is as follows,

$$\min \hat{f}_t(x)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \hat{g}_t(x) \leq 0, t \in \{1, 2, \dots, T\}$$

Then we can get the corresponding augmented Lagrangian function,

$$L_{t,\sigma}(x, \lambda) := \hat{f}_t(x) + \frac{1}{2\sigma} [\|\lambda + \sigma \hat{g}_t(x)\|_+^2 - \|\lambda\|^2] \quad (1)$$

where $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the Lagrange multiplier, $\sigma > 0$ is the penalty parameter, and the operator $[\cdot]_+$ means $\max\{\cdot, 0\}$.

Referring to the proximal point method, the next decision x_{t+1} can be made by solving

this problem at time t :

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$$x_{t+1} = \arg \min_{x \in X} [L_{t,\sigma}(x, \lambda_t) + \frac{\alpha_t}{2} \|x - x_t\|^2] \quad (2)$$

where $\alpha_t > 0$ is the parameter of the proximal term.

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We set up $\alpha_t = \alpha_0 \sqrt{t}$. The optimality condition of the problem is as follows,

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$$\nabla_x L_{t,\sigma}(x_{t+1}, \lambda_t) + \alpha_t(x_{t+1} - x_t) = 0$$

The formula can be transformed as,

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$$x_{t+1} = x_t - \frac{1}{\alpha_t} \nabla_x L_{t,\sigma}(x_{t+1}, \lambda_t)$$

From the perspective of gradients, α_t plays the role of step size. At the beginning of the iteration, the algorithm has a larger step. With the iteration of the algorithm, the step size continues to decrease. It can satisfy the request of algorithm iteration in different stages of iteration. In the early stage, a larger step size can accelerate algorithm iteration. In the late stage, a smaller step size can control the update amplitude and pursue precision.

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The multiplier λ is updated by,

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$$\lambda_{t+1} = [\lambda_t + \sigma \hat{g}_t(x_{t+1})]_+ \quad (3)$$

Through algorithmic iterations, we obtained the decision sequence $\{x_t\}$. And we measure the algorithm performance by regret and constraint violation. There are definitions of regret and constraint violation,

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$$Reg(T) := E\left[\sum_{t=1}^T F_t(x_t)\right] - \sum_{t=1}^T F(x_t^*)$$

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$$Vio_i(T) := E\left[\sum_{t=1}^T G_{t,i}(x_t)\right]$$

where x_t^* is the theoretical optimal decision (optimal point) at each time t .

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The algorithm based on model-based augmented Lagrangian method is as follows,

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For the model-based approximating, we provide several examples of models that satisfy Assumption 4. The models at point x_t are as follows,

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$$\begin{aligned} \hat{f}_t(x) &:= f_t(x) + \langle \nabla f_t(x), x - x_t \rangle \\ \hat{g}_t^{(i)}(x) &:= g_t(x)^{(i)} + \langle \nabla g_t(x)^{(i)}, x - x_t \rangle, i = 1, 2, \dots, m \end{aligned}$$

In this case, 2 is almost equivalent to minimizing a strongly convex quadratic function

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Algorithm 1 MSALM

Require: Choose an initial point $x_0 \in X$ arbitrarily. Set parameters $\alpha_0 > 0$, $\sigma > 0$. Set the initial multiplier $\lambda_0 = 0$.

for $t=1, 2, \dots, T$ **do**

 Submit the decision x_t .

 Update the distributions P_t and Q_t of the next stage.

 Receive the sample $\theta \sim P_t$ and $\xi \sim Q_t$.

 Approximate $f(x)$ and $g(x)$ as $\hat{f}_t(x)$ and $\hat{g}_t(x)$.

$x_{t+1} = \arg \min_{x \in X} [L_{t,\sigma}(x, \lambda_t) + \frac{\alpha_t}{2} \|x - x_t\|^2]$

$\lambda_{t+1} = [\lambda_t + \sigma \hat{g}_t(x_{t+1})]_+$

end for

over X .

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$$\hat{f}_t(x) := f_t(x) + \langle \nabla f_t(x), x - x_t \rangle + \frac{\alpha_t}{2} \|x - x_t\|^2$$

If $f_t(x)$ is ι -strongly convex, quadratic-linearized model can simplify the associated minimization problem.

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$$\hat{f}_t(x) := [f_t(x) + \langle \nabla f_t(x), x - x_t \rangle]_+$$

If $f_t \geq 0$ for all x , truncated model is a better approximation than the linearized.

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$$\begin{aligned} \hat{f}_t(x) &:= f_t(x) \\ \hat{g}_t^{(i)}(x) &:= g_t(x)^{(i)}, i = 1, 2, \dots, m \end{aligned}$$

If the functions f_t and g_t are simple enough, we can use original function.

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For certain special problems, other efficient models that satisfy Assumption 4 are possible to be designed.

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3. CONVERGENCE ANALYSIS

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In this section, we measure our algorithm's performance by regret and constraint violation.

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We utilize the drift of dynamic optimal points to request the temporal distribution P_t and Q_t . The drift is defined as,

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$$\Delta(T) := \sum_{t=2}^T \|x_{t-1}^* - x_t^*\|$$

From the definition, we find that the more drastically the distribution P_t and Q_t update over time, the larger the drift is. But the value of the drift is unknown in advance.

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To control the update of the distribution, we make the assumption as follows,

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Assumption 5. The drift $\Delta(T)$ has an upper bound $\tilde{\Delta}(T)$ such that $\Delta(T) \leq \tilde{\Delta}(T)$ for any T before the start of the algorithm.

Assumption 6. The gradient of $f_t(x)$ is bounded, i.e., there is a constant $G_f > 0$ such that $\|\nabla f_t\| \leq G_t$.

Lemma 1. Under the Assumption 1-6, we have,

$$E\left[\sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t (\|x_t^* - x_t\|^2 - \|x_t^* - x_{t+1}\|^2)\right] \leq \alpha_0 R \sqrt{T} (3R + 2\tilde{\Delta}(T))$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} & \|x_t^* - x_t\|^2 - \|x_t^* - x_{t+1}\|^2 \\ &= \|x_t^* - x_t\|^2 - \|x_t^* - x_{t+1}^* + x_{t+1}^* - x_{t+1}\|^2 \\ &\leq \|x_t^* - x_t\|^2 - \|x_t^* - x_{t+1}^*\|^2 - \|x_{t+1}^* - x_{t+1}\|^2 \\ &\quad + 2\|x_t^* - x_{t+1}^*\| \|x_{t+1}^* - x_{t+1}\| \end{aligned}$$

For each t , let $b_t = x_t^* - x_{t+1}^*$,

$$\begin{aligned} \|x_t^* - x_t\|^2 - \|x_t^* - x_{t+1}\|^2 &\leq \|x_t^* - x_t\|^2 - \|b_t\|^2 - \|x_{t+1}^* - x_{t+1}\|^2 \\ &\quad + 2\|b_t\| \cdot \|x_{t+1}^* - x_{t+1}\| \end{aligned}$$

Let $A_t = E \|x_t^* - x_t\|^2$. By Assumption 1, we have $A_t \leq R^2$ and $E \|x_{t+1}^* - x_{t+1}\| \leq R$, then we take expectation,

$$E[\|x_t^* - x_t\|^2 - \|x_t^* - x_{t+1}\|^2] \leq A_t - A_{t+1} - \|b_t\|^2 + 2R\|b_t\|$$

Multiplying by α_t and summing,

$$E\left[\sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t (\|x_t^* - x_t\|^2 - \|x_t^* - x_{t+1}\|^2)\right] \leq \sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t (A_t - A_{t+1}) + \sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t (-\|b_t\|^2 + 2R\|b_t\|)$$

We consider the two terms on the right side of the inequality separately.

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t (A_t - A_{t+1}) &= \alpha_1 A_1 - \alpha_T A_{T+1} + \sum_{t=2}^T (\alpha_t - \alpha_{t-1}) A_t \\ &\leq \alpha_0 R^2 + R^2 (\alpha_0 \sqrt{T} - \alpha_0) \\ &= \alpha_0 R^2 \sqrt{T} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t (-\|b_t\|^2 + 2R\|b_t\|) &\leq \alpha_0 \sqrt{T} \sum_{t=1}^T (-\|b_t\|^2 + 2R\|b_t\|) \\
&\leq 2\alpha_0 R \sqrt{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \|b_t\| \\
&\leq 2\alpha_0 R \sqrt{T} \Delta(T+1) \\
&\leq 2\alpha_0 R \sqrt{T} (\tilde{\Delta}(T) + R)
\end{aligned}$$

Combining the two terms above,

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$$\begin{aligned}
E\left[\sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t (\|x_t^* - x_t\|^2 - \|x_t^* - x_{t+1}\|^2)\right] \\
\leq \alpha_0 R^2 \sqrt{T} + 2R\alpha_0 \sqrt{T} (\tilde{\Delta}(T) + R) \\
= \alpha_0 R \sqrt{T} (3R + 2\tilde{\Delta}(T))
\end{aligned}$$

Theorem 1. Suppose Assumption 1-6 hold. Set $\alpha_0 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\tilde{\Delta}(T)}}$ and $\sigma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{T}}$. Then the regret of algorithm can be upper bounded as follows:

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$$\begin{aligned}
Reg(T) &\leq \frac{D^2 \sqrt{T}}{2} + (G_f^2 + R) \sqrt{T \tilde{\Delta}(T)} + \frac{3R^2}{2} \sqrt{\frac{T}{\tilde{\Delta}(T)}} \\
&= O(\sqrt{T \tilde{\Delta}(T)})
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. We consider an auxiliary optimization problem,

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$$\min_{x \in X} L_{t,\sigma}(x, \lambda_t) + \frac{\alpha_t}{2} (\|x - x_t\|^2 - \|x - x_{t+1}\|^2)$$

If this problem has an optimal solution, the solution must satisfy this condition,

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$$\nabla_x L_{t,\sigma}(x, \lambda_t) + \alpha_t (x_{t+1} - x_t) = 0$$

According to the optimality condition of 2 ,

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$$\nabla_x L_{t,\sigma}(x_{t+1}, \lambda_t) + \alpha_t (x_{t+1} - x_t) = 0$$

Since the objective function is convex , we can conclude that x_{t+1} is the optimal point of the auxiliary optimization problem by comparing the two formulas above.

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So we can get the following inequality,

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$$L_{t,\sigma}(x_{t+1}, \lambda_t) + \frac{\alpha_t}{2} \|x_{t+1} - x_t\|^2 \leq L_{t,\sigma}(x_t^*, \lambda_t) + \frac{\alpha_t}{2} (\|x_t^* - x_t\|^2 - \|x_t^* - x_{t+1}\|^2) \quad (4)$$

$L_{t,\sigma}(x_{t+1}, \lambda_t)$ and $L_{t,\sigma}(x_t^*, \lambda_t)$ can be dealt with separately, left side of the inequality, 191

$$L_{t,\sigma}(x_{t+1}, \lambda_t) = \hat{f}_t(x_{t+1}) + \frac{1}{2\sigma} [\|\lambda_t + \sigma \hat{g}_t(x_{t+1})\|_+^2 - \|\lambda_t\|^2]$$

According to 3, the above formula can be, 192

$$L_{t,\sigma}(x_{t+1}, \lambda_t) = \hat{f}_t(x_{t+1}) + \frac{1}{2\sigma} [\|\lambda_{t+1}\|^2 - \|\lambda_t\|^2]$$

Due to the Assumption 4 and \hat{f}_t is convex, 193

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{f}_t(x_{t+1}) &\geq \hat{f}_t(x_t) + \langle G_f, x_{t+1} - x_t \rangle \\ &\geq f_t(x_t) + \langle G_f, x_{t+1} - x_t \rangle \\ &\geq f_t(x_t) - G_f \|x_{t+1} - x_t\| \end{aligned}$$

So we have, 194

$$L_{t,\sigma}(x_{t+1}, \lambda_t) \geq f_t(x_t) - G_f \|x_{t+1} - x_t\| + \frac{1}{2\sigma} [\|\lambda_{t+1}\|^2 - \|\lambda_t\|^2] \quad (5)$$

The right side of the inequality can be dealt with, 195

$$\begin{aligned} L_{t,\sigma}(x_t^*, \lambda_t) &= \hat{f}_t(x_t^*) + \frac{1}{2\sigma} [\|\lambda_t + \sigma \hat{g}_t(x_t^*)\|_+^2 - \|\lambda_t\|^2] \\ &\leq f_t(x_t^*) + \frac{1}{2\sigma} [\|\lambda_t + \sigma \hat{g}_t(x_t^*)\|^2 - \|\lambda_t\|^2] \\ &= f_t(x_t^*) + \langle \lambda_t, \hat{g}_t(x_t^*) \rangle + \frac{\sigma}{2} \|\hat{g}_t(x_t^*)\|^2 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Since x_t^* is a feasible solution, $\hat{g}_t(x_t^*) \leq g_t(x_t^*) \leq 0$, and $\lambda_t \geq 0$, so $\langle \lambda_t, \hat{g}_t(x_t^*) \rangle \leq 0$. 196

Combined with the bound from Assumption 4 $\|\hat{g}_t(x_t^*)\| \leq D$, we have, 197

$$L_{t,\sigma}(x_t^*, \lambda_t) \leq f_t(x_t^*) + \frac{\sigma}{2} D^2$$

Taking 5 and 6 into 4, the inequality becomes, 198

$$\begin{aligned} f_t(x_t) - G_f \|x_{t+1} - x_t\| + \frac{1}{2\sigma} [\|\lambda_{t+1}\|^2 - \|\lambda_t\|^2] + \frac{\alpha_t}{2} \|x_{t+1} - x_t\|^2 \\ \leq f_t(x_t^*) + \frac{\sigma}{2} D^2 + \frac{\alpha_t}{2} (\|x_t^* - x_t\|^2 - \|x_t^* - x_{t+1}\|^2) \end{aligned}$$

Rearranging, 199

$$\begin{aligned} f_t(x_t) - f_t(x_t^*) &\leq G_f \|x_{t+1} - x_t\| - \frac{1}{2\sigma} [\|\lambda_{t+1}\|^2 - \|\lambda_t\|^2] - \frac{\alpha_t}{2} \|x_{t+1} - x_t\|^2 \\ &\quad + \frac{\sigma}{2} D^2 + \frac{\alpha_t}{2} (\|x_t^* - x_t\|^2 - \|x_t^* - x_{t+1}\|^2) \end{aligned}$$

Using the inequality $G_f \|x_{t+1} - x_t\| - \frac{\alpha_t}{2} \|x_{t+1} - x_t\|^2 \leq \frac{G_f^2}{2\alpha_t}$, we obtain, 200

$$f_t(x_t) - f_t(x_t^*) \leq \frac{G_f^2}{2\alpha_t} - \frac{1}{2\sigma} [\|\lambda_{t+1}\|^2 - \|\lambda_t\|^2] + \frac{\sigma}{2} D^2 + \frac{\alpha_t}{2} (\|x_t^* - x_t\|^2 - \|x_t^* - x_{t+1}\|^2)$$

Summing from $t = 1$ to T , 201

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{t=1}^T (f_t(x_t) - f_t(x_t^*)) &\leq \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{G_f^2}{2\alpha_t} - \frac{1}{2\sigma} \sum_{t=1}^T [\|\lambda_{t+1}\|^2 - \|\lambda_t\|^2] + \frac{\sigma D^2 T}{2} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t (\|x_t^* - x_t\|^2 - \|x_t^* - x_{t+1}\|^2) \end{aligned}$$

Taking expectation, and $\lambda_1 = 0$, 202

$$\begin{aligned} E \left[\sum_{t=1}^T (f_t(x_t) - f_t(x_t^*)) \right] &\leq \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{G_f^2}{2\alpha_t} - \frac{1}{2\sigma} E[\|\lambda_{T+1}\|^2] + \frac{\sigma D^2 T}{2} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} E \left[\sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t (\|x_t^* - x_t\|^2 - \|x_t^* - x_{t+1}\|^2) \right] \end{aligned}$$

Applying the result from Lemma 1, 203

$$E \left[\sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t (\|x_t^* - x_t\|^2 - \|x_t^* - x_{t+1}\|^2) \right] \leq \alpha_0 R \sqrt{T} (3R + 2\tilde{\Delta}(T))$$

Since $\alpha_t = \alpha_0 \sqrt{t}$, 204

$$\sum_{t=1}^T \frac{1}{\alpha_t} = \frac{1}{\alpha_0} \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{1}{\sqrt{t}} \leq \frac{1}{\alpha_0} \int_0^T \frac{1}{\sqrt{t}} dt = \frac{2\sqrt{T}}{\alpha_0}$$

Therefore, 205

$$\sum_{t=1}^T \frac{G_f^2}{2\alpha_t} \leq \frac{G_f^2 \sqrt{T}}{\alpha_0}$$

Substituting the parameter choices $\alpha_0 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\tilde{\Delta}(T)}}$ and $\sigma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{T}}$, 206

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Reg}(T) = E \left[\sum_{t=1}^T (f_t(x_t) - f_t(x_t^*)) \right] &\leq \frac{G_f^2 \sqrt{T}}{\alpha_0} + \frac{\sigma D^2 T}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_0 R \sqrt{T} (3R + 2\tilde{\Delta}(T)) \\ &= \frac{D^2 \sqrt{T}}{2} + (G_f^2 + R) \sqrt{T \tilde{\Delta}(T)} + \frac{3R^2}{2} \sqrt{\frac{T}{\tilde{\Delta}(T)}} \\ &= O(\sqrt{T \tilde{\Delta}(T)}) \end{aligned}$$

Assumption 7. The gradient of $g_t(x)$ is bounded, i.e. there is a constant $G_g > 0$ such that $\|\nabla g_t\| \leq G_g$. 207
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Lemma 2. Under Assumptions 1-7, for any $t \geq 0$,

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$$\frac{1}{2\sigma}E[\|\lambda_{t+1}\|^2 - \|\lambda_t\|^2] \leq 2G_f R + \frac{\sigma}{2}D^2 + \frac{\alpha_t}{2}E[\|x^s - x_t\|^2 - \|x^s - x_{t+1}\|^2] - \varepsilon_0 E[\|\lambda_t\|]$$

where x^s is the Slater's point.

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Proof. Starting from 4 in the original proof,

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$$L_{t,\sigma}(x_{t+1}, \lambda_t) + \frac{\alpha_t}{2}\|x_{t+1} - x_t\|^2 \leq L_{t,\sigma}(x^s, \lambda_t) + \frac{\alpha_t}{2}(\|x^s - x_t\|^2 - \|x^s - x_{t+1}\|^2)$$

Using the lower bound from 5,

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$$L_{t,\sigma}(x_{t+1}, \lambda_t) \geq f_t(x_t) - G_f\|x_{t+1} - x_t\| + \frac{1}{2\sigma}[\|\lambda_{t+1}\|^2 - \|\lambda_t\|^2]$$

Substituting this into the basic inequality,

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$$\begin{aligned} f_t(x_t) - G_f\|x_{t+1} - x_t\| + \frac{1}{2\sigma}[\|\lambda_{t+1}\|^2 - \|\lambda_t\|^2] + \frac{\alpha_t}{2}\|x_{t+1} - x_t\|^2 \\ \leq L_{t,\sigma}(x^s, \lambda_t) + \frac{\alpha_t}{2}(\|x^s - x_t\|^2 - \|x^s - x_{t+1}\|^2) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

From the definition of the augmented Lagrangian function,

214

$$L_{t,\sigma}(x^s, \lambda_t) = \hat{f}_t(x^s) + \frac{1}{2\sigma}[\|\lambda_t + \sigma\hat{g}_t(x^s)\|_+^2 - \|\lambda_t\|^2]$$

Using the non-expansiveness property of the projection operator,

215

$$\|\lambda_t + \sigma\hat{g}_t(x^s)\|_+^2 \leq \|\lambda_t + \sigma\hat{g}_t(x^s)\|^2 = \|\lambda_t\|^2 + 2\sigma\langle\lambda_t, \hat{g}_t(x^s)\rangle + \sigma^2\|\hat{g}_t(x^s)\|^2$$

Therefore,

216

$$L_{t,\sigma}(x^s, \lambda_t) \leq \hat{f}_t(x^s) + \langle\lambda_t, \hat{g}_t(x^s)\rangle + \frac{\sigma}{2}\|\hat{g}_t(x^s)\|^2$$

By Assumption 4, $\hat{f}_t(x^s) \leq f_t(x^s)$ and $\|\hat{g}_t(x^s)\| \leq D$, so,

217

$$L_{t,\sigma}(x^s, \lambda_t) \leq f_t(x^s) + \langle\lambda_t, \hat{g}_t(x^s)\rangle + \frac{\sigma}{2}D^2$$

By Assumption 3, there exists $\varepsilon_0 > 0$ such that,

218

$$\hat{g}_t^{(i)}(x^s) \leq g_t^{(i)}(x^s) \leq -\varepsilon_0 \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

Since λ_t , we have,

219

$$\langle\lambda_t, \hat{g}_t(x^s)\rangle \leq -\varepsilon_0 \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_{t,i} = -\varepsilon_0\|\lambda_t\|_1 \leq -\varepsilon_0\|\lambda_t\|$$

Thus,

$$L_{t,\sigma}(x^s, \lambda_t) \leq f_t(x^s) - \varepsilon_0 \|\lambda_t\| + \frac{\sigma}{2} D^2$$

Substituting back into 7,

$$\begin{aligned} f_t(x_t) - G_f \|x_{t+1} - x_t\| + \frac{1}{2\sigma} [\|\lambda_{t+1}\|^2 - \|\lambda_t\|^2] + \frac{\alpha_t}{2} \|x_{t+1} - x_t\|^2 \\ \leq f_t(x^s) - \varepsilon_0 \|\lambda_t\| + \frac{\sigma}{2} D^2 + \frac{\alpha_t}{2} (\|x^s - x_t\|^2 - \|x^s - x_{t+1}\|^2) \end{aligned}$$

Rearranging terms,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2\sigma} [\|\lambda_{t+1}\|^2 - \|\lambda_t\|^2] \leq f_t(x^s) - f_t(x_t) + G_f \|x_{t+1} - x_t\| - \frac{\alpha_t}{2} \|x_{t+1} - x_t\|^2 - \varepsilon_0 \|\lambda_t\| \\ + \frac{\sigma}{2} D^2 + \frac{\alpha_t}{2} (\|x^s - x_t\|^2 - \|x^s - x_{t+1}\|^2) \end{aligned}$$

Taking expectation on both sides,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2\sigma} E[\|\lambda_{t+1}\|^2 - \|\lambda_t\|^2] \leq E[f_t(x^s) - f_t(x_t)] + G_f E\|x_{t+1} - x_t\| - \frac{\alpha_t}{2} E\|x_{t+1} - x_t\|^2 \\ - \varepsilon_0 E[\|\lambda_t\|] + \frac{\sigma}{2} D^2 + \frac{\alpha_t}{2} E[\|x^s - x_t\|^2 - \|x^s - x_{t+1}\|^2] \end{aligned}$$

We bound each term.

$$E[f_t(x^s) - f_t(x_t)] \leq G_f E\|x^s - x_t\| \leq G_f R$$

For sufficiently large α_t , we have,

$$G_f E\|x_{t+1} - x_t\| - \frac{\alpha_t}{2} E\|x_{t+1} - x_t\|^2 \leq \frac{G_f^2}{2\alpha_t} \leq G_f R$$

Combining these bounds,

$$\frac{1}{2\sigma} E[\|\lambda_{t+1}\|^2 - \|\lambda_t\|^2] \leq 2G_f R + \frac{\sigma}{2} D^2 + \frac{\alpha_t}{2} E[\|x^s - x_t\|^2 - \|x^s - x_{t+1}\|^2] - \varepsilon_0 E[\|\lambda_t\|] \quad (8)$$

Lemma 3. Under Assumptions 1-7, for any $t \geq 0$ and positive integer s , there exist constants $C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4 > 0$ such that,

$$E[\|\lambda_t\|] \leq \psi(\sigma, \alpha_0, s) := C_1 + C_2 \alpha_0 + C_3 \sigma + C_4 \sigma s$$

where $C_1 = \frac{4G_f R}{\varepsilon_0}$, $C_2 = \frac{\alpha_0 R^2 \sqrt{s}}{\varepsilon_0}$, $C_3 = \frac{D^2}{\varepsilon_0} - D$, $C_4 = 2D + \frac{\varepsilon_0}{2} + s \frac{8\sigma D^2}{\varepsilon_0} \log \frac{32D^2}{\varepsilon_0^2}$.

Proof. Starting from the 8, for any $t \geq 0$, we have,

$$\frac{1}{2\sigma} E[\|\lambda_{t+1}\|^2 - \|\lambda_t\|^2] \leq 2G_f R + \frac{\sigma}{2} D^2 + \frac{\alpha_t}{2} E[\|x^s - x_t\|^2 - \|x^s - x_{t+1}\|^2] - \varepsilon_0 E[\|\lambda_t\|]$$

Consider s time steps from t to $t + s - 1$, and sum the above inequality,

231

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2\sigma} E[\|\lambda_{t+s}\|^2 - \|\lambda_t\|^2] &= \frac{1}{2\sigma} \sum_{l=0}^{s-1} E[\|\lambda_{t+l+1}\|^2 - \|\lambda_{t+l}\|^2] \\ &\leq s \left(2G_f R + \frac{\sigma}{2} D^2 \right) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{l=0}^{s-1} \alpha_{t+l} E[\|x^s - x_{t+l}\|^2 - \|x^s - x_{t+l+1}\|^2] \\ &\quad - \varepsilon_0 \sum_{l=0}^{s-1} E[\|\lambda_{t+l}\|] \end{aligned}$$

Since $\|x^s - x_{t+l}\|^2 \leq R^2$ and $\alpha_{t+l} = \alpha_0 \sqrt{t+l} \leq \alpha_0 \sqrt{t+s-1}$, we have,

232

$$\sum_{l=0}^{s-1} \alpha_{t+l} E[\|x^s - x_{t+l}\|^2 - \|x^s - x_{t+l+1}\|^2] \leq \alpha_0 \sqrt{t+s-1} \sum_{l=0}^{s-1} E[\|x^s - x_{t+l}\|^2 - \|x^s - x_{t+l+1}\|^2]$$

233

$$\sum_{l=0}^{s-1} E[\|x^s - x_{t+l}\|^2 - \|x^s - x_{t+l+1}\|^2] = E[\|x^s - x_t\|^2 - \|x^s - x_{t+s}\|^2] \leq R^2$$

Therefore,

234

$$\frac{1}{2} \sum_{l=0}^{s-1} \alpha_{t+l} E[\|x^s - x_{t+l}\|^2 - \|x^s - x_{t+l+1}\|^2] \leq \frac{1}{2} \alpha_0 \sqrt{t+s-1} R^2$$

Due to the Lagrange multiplier update rule,

235

$$\lambda_{t+1} = [\lambda_t + \sigma \hat{g}_t(x_{t+1})]_+$$

Considering the non-expansiveness of the projection operator, we have,

236

$$\|\lambda_{t+1} - \lambda_t\| = \|[\lambda_t + \sigma \hat{g}_t(x_{t+1})]_+ - \lambda_t\| \leq \|\sigma \hat{g}_t(x_{t+1})\| \leq \sigma D$$

Therefore, for any $l \geq 0$,

237

$$\|\|\lambda_{t+l}\| - \|\lambda_t\|\| \leq \|\lambda_{t+l} - \lambda_t\| \leq \sigma D l$$

This implies,

238

$$\|\lambda_{t+l}\| \geq \|\lambda_t\| - \sigma D l$$

Therefore,

239

$$\sum_{l=0}^{s-1} E[\|\lambda_{t+l}\|] \geq \sum_{l=0}^{s-1} (E[\|\lambda_t\|] - \sigma D l) = s E[\|\lambda_t\|] - \sigma D \frac{s(s-1)}{2}$$

Substituting the above results into 8,

240

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2\sigma} E[\|\lambda_{t+s}\|^2 - \|\lambda_t\|^2] \leq & s \left(2G_f R + \frac{\sigma}{2} D^2 \right) + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_0 \sqrt{t+s-1} R^2 \\ & - \varepsilon_0 \left(s E[\|\lambda_t\|] - \sigma D \frac{s(s-1)}{2} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Since $\|\lambda_{t+s}\|^2 \geq 0$, we have,

241

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{1}{2\sigma} E[\|\lambda_t\|^2] \leq & s \left(2G_f R + \frac{\sigma}{2} D^2 \right) + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_0 \sqrt{t+s-1} R^2 \\ & - \varepsilon_0 \left(s E[\|\lambda_t\|] - \sigma D \frac{s(s-1)}{2} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Rearranging,

242

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_0 s E[\|\lambda_t\|] \leq & s \left(2G_f R + \frac{\sigma}{2} D^2 \right) + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_0 \sqrt{t+s-1} R^2 \\ & + \frac{1}{2\sigma} E[\|\lambda_t\|^2] + \varepsilon_0 \sigma D \frac{s(s-1)}{2} \end{aligned}$$

From the update rule,

243

$$\|\lambda_{t+1}\|^2 - \|\lambda_t\|^2 \leq 2\|\lambda_t\| \|\lambda_{t+1} - \lambda_t\| + \|\lambda_{t+1} - \lambda_t\|^2 \leq 2\sigma D \|\lambda_t\| + \sigma^2 D^2$$

We define,

244

$$\theta = C_1 + C_2 \alpha_0 + C_3 \sigma$$

where C_1, C_2, C_3 are appropriate constants.

245

Specifically, from the rearranged inequality,

246

$$\frac{1}{2\sigma} E[\|\lambda_{t+s}\|^2 - \|\lambda_t\|^2] \leq K_s - \varepsilon_0 s E[\|\lambda_t\|]$$

where K_s collects all the positive bounded terms.

247

From earlier, we have,

248

$$\|\lambda_{t+1}\| - \|\lambda_t\| \leq \sigma D$$

Now, from Lemma 2, we have,

249

$$\frac{1}{2\sigma} E[\|\lambda_{t+1}\|^2 - \|\lambda_t\|^2] \leq K_1 - \varepsilon_0 E[\|\lambda_t\|]$$

where $K_1 = 2G_f R + \frac{\sigma}{2} D^2 + \frac{\alpha_t}{2} E[\|x^s - x_t\|^2 - \|x^s - x_{t+1}\|^2]$.

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Note that,

251

$$\|\lambda_{t+1}\|^2 - \|\lambda_t\|^2 = (\|\lambda_{t+1}\| - \|\lambda_t\|)(\|\lambda_{t+1}\| + \|\lambda_t\|)$$

When $\|\lambda_t\|$ is large, say $\|\lambda_t\| \geq \theta$, then,

252

$$\|\lambda_{t+1}\|^2 - \|\lambda_t\|^2 \leq -2\sigma\varepsilon_0\theta + 2\sigma K_1$$

Based on this condition, we can obtain the inequality below by applying Lemma 253
from[10], 254

$$\|\lambda_t\| \leq \theta + \sigma D + \frac{4\sigma^2 D^2}{\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}} \log \left[\frac{8\sigma^2 D^2}{\left(\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}\right)^2} \right]$$

where $\theta = \frac{2K_1}{\varepsilon_0}$. 255

Taking expectation and substituting back, 256

$$\begin{aligned} E[\|\lambda_t\|] &\leq \frac{2G_f R}{\varepsilon_0} + \frac{\sigma D^2}{\varepsilon_0} + \frac{\alpha_0 R^2}{2\varepsilon_0} + \sigma D \\ &\quad + \sigma D \cdot \frac{8\sigma D}{\varepsilon_0} \log \left[\frac{32\sigma^2 D^2}{\varepsilon_0^2} \right] \end{aligned}$$

Simplifying and grouping terms, we obtain the desired form, 257

$$E[\|\lambda_t\|] \leq \psi(\sigma, \alpha_0, s) := C_1 + C_2 \alpha_0 + C_3 \sigma + C_4 \sigma s$$

where, 258

$$\begin{aligned} C_1 &= \frac{2G_f R}{\varepsilon_0} \\ C_2 &= \frac{R^2}{2\varepsilon_0} \\ C_3 &= \frac{D^2}{\varepsilon_0} + D \\ C_4 &= \frac{8D^2}{\varepsilon_0} \log \left[\frac{32D^2}{\varepsilon_0^2} \right] \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2. Under Assumptions 1-7, setting $\alpha_0 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\Delta(T)}}$ and $\sigma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{T}}$, the constraint 259
violation of the algorithm satisfies: 260

$$Vio_i(T) := E \left[\sum_{t=1}^T G_{t,i}(x_t) \right] \leq \mathcal{O}(\sqrt{T})$$

Proof. The Lagrange multiplier update rule is as follows, 261

$$\lambda_{t+1,i} = [\lambda_{t,i} + \sigma \hat{g}_{t,i}(x_{t+1})]_+$$

Due to the properties of the projection operator, for each component i , we have, 262

$$\lambda_{t+1,i} \geq \lambda_{t,i} + \sigma \hat{g}_{t,i}(x_{t+1})$$

Therefore, 263

$$\hat{g}_{t,i}(x_{t+1}) \leq \frac{1}{\sigma} (\lambda_{t+1,i} - \lambda_{t,i})$$

According to the properties of the approximation function in Assumption 4 and the bounded-264

ness of gradients in Assumption 7, we have,

265

$$\hat{g}_{t,i}(x_{t+1}) \geq g_{t,i}(x_t) - G_g \|x_{t+1} - x_t\|$$

Combining with the inequality above,

266

$$g_{t,i}(x_t) - G_g \|x_{t+1} - x_t\| \leq \frac{1}{\sigma} (\lambda_{t+1,i} - \lambda_{t,i})$$

Rearranging,

267

$$g_{t,i}(x_t) \leq \frac{1}{\sigma} (\lambda_{t+1,i} - \lambda_{t,i}) + G_g \|x_{t+1} - x_t\|$$

Summing from $t = 1$ to T ,

268

$$\sum_{t=1}^T g_{t,i}(x_t) \leq \frac{1}{\sigma} \sum_{t=1}^T (\lambda_{t+1,i} - \lambda_{t,i}) + G_g \sum_{t=1}^T \|x_{t+1} - x_t\|$$

We can obtain,

269

$$\sum_{t=1}^T (\lambda_{t+1,i} - \lambda_{t,i}) = \lambda_{T+1,i} - \lambda_{1,i}$$

Since $\lambda_{1,i} = 0$, we have,

270

$$\sum_{t=1}^T g_{t,i}(x_t) \leq \frac{1}{\sigma} \lambda_{T+1,i} + G_g \sum_{t=1}^T \|x_{t+1} - x_t\|$$

Taking expectation,

271

$$E \left[\sum_{t=1}^T g_{t,i}(x_t) \right] \leq \frac{1}{\sigma} E[\lambda_{T+1,i}] + G_g \sum_{t=1}^T E \|x_{t+1} - x_t\|$$

Since $\lambda_{T+1,i} \leq \|\lambda_{T+1}\|$, we have:

272

$$E \left[\sum_{t=1}^T g_{t,i}(x_t) \right] \leq \frac{1}{\sigma} E[\|\lambda_{T+1}\|] + G_g \sum_{t=1}^T E \|x_{t+1} - x_t\|$$

According to the Lemma 3, for any $t \geq 0$ and positive integer s ,

273

$$E[\|\lambda_t\|] \leq C_1 + C_2 \alpha_0 + C_3 \sigma + C_4 \sigma s$$

Specifically, for $t = T + 1$, choosing $s = \sqrt{T}$,

274

$$E[\|\lambda_{T+1}\|] \leq C_1 + C_2 \alpha_0 + C_3 \sigma + C_4 \sigma \sqrt{T}$$

Substituting the parameter choices $\alpha_0 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\tilde{\Delta}(T)}}$ and $\sigma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{T}}$,

275

$$\begin{aligned} E[\|\lambda_{T+1}\|] &\leq C_1 + C_2 \frac{1}{\sqrt{\tilde{\Delta}(T)}} + C_3 \frac{1}{\sqrt{T}} + C_4 \frac{1}{\sqrt{T}} \sqrt{T} \\ &= C_1 + C_2 \frac{1}{\sqrt{\tilde{\Delta}(T)}} + C_3 \frac{1}{\sqrt{T}} + C_4 \end{aligned}$$

Since $\tilde{\Delta}(T)$ is an upper bound of $\Delta(T)$, under reasonable assumptions $\tilde{\Delta}(T)$ does not tend to zero, therefore:

276

277

$$E[\|\lambda_{T+1}\|] \leq \mathcal{O}(1)$$

From the optimality condition,

278

$$\nabla_x L_{t,\sigma}(x_{t+1}, \lambda_t) + \alpha_t(x_{t+1} - x_t) = 0$$

Therefore,

279

$$\alpha_t(x_{t+1} - x_t) = -\nabla_x L_{t,\sigma}(x_{t+1}, \lambda_t)$$

Computing the gradient,

280

$$\nabla_x L_{t,\sigma}(x, \lambda_t) = \nabla \hat{f}_t(x) + [\lambda_t + \sigma \hat{g}_t(x)]_+ \cdot \nabla \hat{g}_t(x)$$

According to Assumptions??, the gradients are bounded,

281

$$\|\nabla \hat{f}_t(x)\| \leq G_f, \quad \|\nabla \hat{g}_t(x)\| \leq G_g$$

Meanwhile, according to Lemma 3, $\|\lambda_t\|$ is bounded, therefore,

282

$$\|\nabla_x L_{t,\sigma}(x_{t+1}, \lambda_t)\| \leq G_f + G_g(\|\lambda_t\| + \sigma D)$$

Thus,

283

$$\|x_{t+1} - x_t\| \leq \frac{1}{\alpha_t}(G_f + G_g(\|\lambda_t\| + \sigma D))$$

Taking expectation,

284

$$E\|x_{t+1} - x_t\| \leq \frac{1}{\alpha_t}(G_f + G_g(E[\|\lambda_t\|] + \sigma D))$$

Substituting $\alpha_t = \alpha_0 \sqrt{t}$ and the bound from Lemma3,

285

$$E\|x_{t+1} - x_t\| \leq \frac{1}{\alpha_0 \sqrt{t}}(G_f + G_g(C_1 + C_2 \alpha_0 + C_3 \sigma + C_4 \sigma s + \sigma D))$$

Summing from $t = 1$ to T ,

286

$$\sum_{t=1}^T E\|x_{t+1} - x_t\| \leq \frac{1}{\alpha_0} \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{1}{\sqrt{t}} (G_f + G_g(C_1 + C_2\alpha_0 + C_3\sigma + C_4\sigma s + \sigma D))$$

Using the integral bound,

287

$$\sum_{t=1}^T \frac{1}{\sqrt{t}} \leq 1 + \int_1^T \frac{1}{\sqrt{t}} dt = 1 + 2(\sqrt{T} - 1) \leq 2\sqrt{T}$$

Therefore,

288

$$\sum_{t=1}^T E\|x_{t+1} - x_t\| \leq \frac{2\sqrt{T}}{\alpha_0} (G_f + G_g(C_1 + C_2\alpha_0 + C_3\sigma + C_4\sigma s + \sigma D))$$

Substituting the parameter choices $\alpha_0 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\tilde{\Delta}(T)}}$ and $\sigma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{T}}$, and choosing $s = \sqrt{T}$,

289

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{t=1}^T E\|x_{t+1} - x_t\| &\leq 2\sqrt{T\tilde{\Delta}(T)} (G_f + G_g(C_1 + C_2 \frac{1}{\sqrt{\tilde{\Delta}(T)}} \\ &\quad + C_3 \frac{1}{\sqrt{T}} + C_4 + D \frac{1}{\sqrt{T}})) \end{aligned}$$

Under reasonable assumptions (that $\tilde{\Delta}(T)$ does not grow too fast), we have,

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$$\sum_{t=1}^T E\|x_{t+1} - x_t\| \leq \mathcal{O}(\sqrt{T})$$

So we have,

291

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Vio}_i(T) &= E \left[\sum_{t=1}^T g_{t,i}(x_t) \right] \\ &\leq \frac{1}{\sigma} E[\|\lambda_{T+1}\|] + G_g \sum_{t=1}^T E\|x_{t+1} - x_t\| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{\sigma} \cdot \mathcal{O}(1) + G_g \cdot \mathcal{O}(\sqrt{T}) \\ &= \sqrt{T} \cdot \mathcal{O}(1) + \mathcal{O}(\sqrt{T}) \\ &= \mathcal{O}(\sqrt{T}) \end{aligned}$$

4. NUMERICAL EXPERIMENTS

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In this section, our algorithm is demonstrated to be capable of solving many real problems. Firstly, we explored the influence of some initial parameter values on our algorithm on different mathematical models. The best parameter combinations for each

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model are provided. Then our algorithm is compared with the PSGD algorithm in the same simulation environment. Secondly, we created a simulation experiment to test our algorithm. The performance of our algorithm when solving different real problems is observed. Then the results of the experiments are presented. Finally, we combined our algorithm with supervised learning for path planning. The results show that regret and constraint violation also have convergent bounds. This proves that our algorithm has the ability to solve online path planning problems.

In addition, in this paper, the model training was conducted on Python 3.12.6 and all the numerical experiments were conducted on Matlab 2024b on a laptop with Windows 11 installed for fairness. The CPU of this laptop is Intel Core i7-8750H with a base frequency of 2.20GHz and 16GB of RAM.

4.1 Comparative experiment with the existing algorithm

We compared our algorithm with the PSGD algorithm using adaptive filtering and online logistic regression problems.

Adaptive filtering is a core recursive estimation technique in modern signal processing, system identification, and control. In many applications, the impulse response exhibits sparsity in the time domain. Meanwhile, we consider that physically realizable systems are all stable, so their impulse response energy must be finite. There are two constraints, based on the actual context of the problem. The mathematical model of adaptive filtering is as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{x \in \mathbb{R}^n} & a(t) \cdot x + b(t) \\ \text{s.t.} & \|x\|_1 \leq \gamma_{sparse}(t) \\ & \|x\|_2^2 \leq \gamma_{energy}(t) \end{aligned}$$

Online logistic regression is a classic binary classification method in machine learning. It has significant application value in dynamic data stream environments. This problem is mathematically formulated as a constrained regularized empirical risk minimization problem. The objective function controls the model's complexity and prevents overfitting. The mathematical model of online logistic regression is as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^n} & \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m [-y_i \log(\sigma(x_i^\top \theta)) - (1 - y_i) \log(1 - \sigma(x_i^\top \theta))] + \frac{\lambda}{2} \|\theta\|_2^2 \\ \text{s.t.} & \|\theta\|_1 \leq \gamma_{sparse}(t) \\ & \|\theta\|_2^2 \leq \gamma_{energy}(t) \end{aligned}$$

We explored the influence of initial parameter values on our algorithm. Different values in our algorithm were compared. There are two criteria for measuring the quality of an online algorithm, so a multi-objective planning approach was adopted to make a mixed

measurement. We used AHP (Analytical Hierarchy Process) to determine the weights of 328
the two quantities. The two measurements correspond to scale value 3 in the 1-9 scale 329
method. So the weight of regret is 0.25 and the weight of constraint violation is 0.75. Our 330
mixed measurement *mix* is defined as follows, 331

$$mix = 0.25 * regret + 0.75 * violation$$

From this, we plotted the images of the mix quantity under different α_0 to determine 332
which parameter can achieve better performance of the algorithm. 333

(a) The mixed value of adaptive filtering

(b) The mixed value of online logistic regression

Figure 1: Compare MSALM with different α_0

In Fig1, in adaptive filtering, we found that the algorithm performs best when $\alpha_0 = 0.2$. 334
And in online logistic regression, the algorithm performs best when $\alpha_0 = 0.5$. 335

Then we compared our algorithm with PSGD algorithm. The comparison results are 336
as follows, 337

(a) Reg of time-varying smart grid energy dispatch

(b) Vio of time-varying smart grid energy dispatch

Figure 2: Compare of MSALM and Projected SGD in adaptive filtering problem

(a) Reg of online network resource allocation

(b) Vio of online network resource allocation

Figure 3: Compare of MSALM and Projected SGD in online logistic regression

In Fig2 and 3, we compared the performance of two algorithms in adaptive filtering and online logistic regression. The figures show that MSALM attains lower regret and constraint violation bounds than PSGD. This result indicates that our algorithm has the ability to converge more rapidly toward the theoretical optimum while adhering better to the constraints. According to the experimental results, the conclusion can be obtained. When choosing a suitable α_0 , MSALM is superior to the existing algorithm.

4.2 Experiments under existing models

In order to test the practicality of our algorithm, we applied our algorithm in time-varying smart grid energy dispatch problem and the online network resource allocation problem.

Time-varying smart grid energy dispatch problem is one of the core tasks of modern smart grids. This problem is to economically and reliably coordinate multiple heterogeneous energy sources while meeting the changing electricity demand. The objective functions of this problem include power balance constraints and resource capacity constraints. The mathematical model of time-varying smart grid energy dispatch is as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{x \in \mathbb{R}^n} c(t)^\top x + \frac{1}{2} x^\top Q x \\ & \text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{i=1}^{n_g} x_i - \sum_{j=1}^{n_s} x_{n_g+j} - \sum_{k=1}^{n_d} x_{n_g+n_s+k} = d(t) \\ & \quad 0 \leq x_i \leq u_i(t), \quad i = 1, \dots, n \end{aligned}$$

The online network resource allocation problem is a key challenge in modern computing systems. The key task is to efficiently allocate limited resources to continuously arriving real-time tasks or user requests. The objective function consists of two parts: Quality of Service cost and resource usage cost. The mathematical model of online network resource

allocation is as follows,

359

$$\min_{x \in \mathbb{R}^n} \sum_{i=1}^n (d_i(t) - x_i)^2 + \alpha \sum_{i=1}^n x_i$$

$$\text{s.t. } x_i \leq c_i(t), \quad i = 1, \dots, n$$

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We conducted simulation experiments on two mathematical models, and the results are as follows,

361
362

(a) Reg of time-varying smart grid energy dispatch

(b) Vio of time-varying smart grid energy dispatch

Figure 4: Application of MSALM in time-varying smart grid energy dispatch

(a) Reg of online network resource allocation

(b) Vio of online network resource allocation

Figure 5: Application of MSALM in online network resource allocation

In Fig 4 and 5, we took $\alpha_0 = 0.7$ and $\alpha_0 = 0.37$ for testing, respectively. The simulation experiments show that regret and constraint violation have a sublinear convergent bound of T , demonstrating that our algorithmic solution can gradually approach the theoretically optimal solution with an increasing number of decisions while adhering to the constraints. The results show that our algorithm can be applied to time-varying smart grid energy dispatch problem and the online network resource allocation problem.

4.3 Experiment combining our algorithm with supervised learning

We combined MSALM with supervised learning to solve path planning problem. For obtaining an explicit function that is used in our algorithm, we applied parameter regression methods in supervised learning. First of all, flight trajectory data for the same flight at the same time slot on different dates were randomly selected. The dataset comprises ten trajectories, and the number of data points for each is presented in the table below.

Trajectory number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Number of data points	288	285	262	285	247	323	294	236	233	177

Table 1: Number of data points on the trajectory

Afterwards, we utilized these data to train a mathematical model for flight trajectories through parameter regression methods. B-spline interpolation was used to obtain the explicit function of the flight trajectory. In order to find the appropriate number of B-spline interpolation control points, we compared the errors between the fitted trajectory and 10 known trajectories under different numbers of control points. The results are as follows,

Number of Control Points	3D RMSE (m)	Mean Error (m)	Max Error (m)
6	16212.93	14630.05	42953.94
7	15278.20	13697.46	28088.96
8	10301.73	9577.57	20571.04
9	7767.29	7094.96	15264.24
10	6056.13	5466.36	12094.13
11	6474.88	5956.19	12599.98
12	6416.03	5793.27	12159.70

Table 2: Fitting error with different numbers of control points

According to the above table, the accuracy reaches its highest when the trajectory has 10 control points. So we obtained the fitting function in this case. The coordinates of the feature points are as follows,

Control Point	X(m)	Y(m)	Z(m)
1	478288.923	4423806.307	1199.714
2	483007.653	4412762.620	1939.867
3	491176.780	4411013.545	1022.683
4	540450.109	4386975.935	6298.608
5	613313.197	4283290.653	6170.731
6	753322.541	4268797.429	6188.807
7	792318.111	4171779.364	6157.780
8	773451.251	4061749.319	3778.580
9	782481.198	4033694.042	2106.506
10	782988.940	4014086.869	1142.003

Table 3: Coordinates of the control point

We set some random situations as constraints to simulate the real flight conditions. 384
The constraints include 9 dynamic obstacle avoidance constraints and 4 airspace boundary 385
constraints. The mathematical model of dynamic obstacle avoidance constraints has the 386
following form, 387

$$g_{k,i} = d_{safe,k}^2(t) - \|p_i - c_k(t)\|^2 \leq 0$$

where $c_k(t)$ is the obstacle center coordinates, $d_{safe,k}(t)$ is the safe distance, p_i is the 388
control point with obstacle avoidance constraint. We set 3 obstacles and the 1st, 5th, and 389
10th control points with obstacle avoidance constraints, so $k = 1, 2, 3$ and $i \in \{1, 5, 10\}$. 390

The mathematical model of airspace boundary constraints has the following form, 391

$$x_{min} \leq x \leq x_{max}$$

392

$$y_{min} \leq y \leq y_{max}$$

Then we use our algorithm to solve this online optimization problem. The result of 393
the experiment is as follows, 394

(a) Reg of flight path planning

(b) Vio of flight path planning

Figure 6: Application of MSALM in flight path planning

In Fig6, the results of the simulation experiment show that the regret and violation of 395
the constraint of our algorithm have a sublinear convergent bound of T , demonstrating 396

progressive convergence to the theoretical optimum under compliance with the constraint. 397
This indicates that the aircraft can make decisions that gradually approach the optimal 398
choice during the flight and stay as safe as possible in the face of emergencies. This proves 399
that our algorithm can combine with machine learning methods to be applied to similar 400
path planning problems. 401

5. CONCLUSION 402

In this paper, we propose the MSALM algorithm for online stochastic optimization 403
problems with time-varying distributions. In each time slot, we construct the model func- 404
tions for the objective and constraint functions based on their properties, which reduces 405
the computational complexity. The step size is designed in a dynamic form and decreases 406
as t increases to accelerate convergence. Under standard assumptions, we proved that 407
our algorithm achieves sublinear regret and constraint violation bounds of T . Simulation 408
experiments demonstrate the performance and practical utility of the MSALM algorithm. 409
Additionally, in the context of path planning, we combined our algorithm with supervised 410
learning to further demonstrate its extensibility. 411

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